

UNDERSTANDING THE PHENOMENON OF

FAKE NEWS

The Indian Story

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ABSTRACT

The report ‘Understanding the Phenomenon of Fake News: The Indian Story’ is an exercise in understanding the phenomenon of fake news spreading in India at a massive scale. It attempts to understand what constitutes Fake News before moving on to explore the the interests and discourses that promote the generation of fake news across various platforms used in India. The report also aims to research the content of fake news and its implications, explore the trajectory of its growth in India against events of national importance that have occurred in the last year, and to document the institutional response whatsoever to the same. The report understands fake news as misleading information meant to benefit a certain purpose, and attempts to explore the various possible dimensions – political, economic, and social – that can answer the question of intent. It contextualizes the phenomenon of fake news spreading in India to the wider era of – what some consider – ‘Post-Truth’, where platforms like social media seem open to those who want to tweak or colour the objective truth and sell it to an unsuspecting audience still grappling with the vast expanse and pace of technological innovation. The methodology employed for this is an analysis of misinformation debunked on various fact-checking websites operating in India – Alt News, Boom Live, Factly to name a few. A quick glance at these websites highlights the political nature of misinformation spread through platforms like Whatsapp and Facebook, targeting people of different religions, political affiliation and ethnicities, at times around significant events like the state assembly elections, attack on CRPF forces in Pulwama etc, possibly to create divisive unrest. The digital space of information has real-life consequences that affect the social and political action of citizens. The report also aims to document the institutional response on the part of the Indian government as well as social media platforms, and provide policy recommendations to curb the menace of fake news in India.

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INTRODUCTION:

June 2018 saw reports of 2 men, later identified as Nilotpal Das (29) and Abhijit Nath (30), artists on vacation, tortured and lynched to death by an ‘inebriated’ mob in Assam’s Panjuri, a Karbi tribal village. The villagers suspected them of being child abductors thanks to ‘news’ doing the rounds on social media claiming incidents of children-abduction on the rise in the area. What followed was a gruesome video showing one of the victims bleeding, pleading to be spared, trying to convince the mob that he was Assamese too, to no avail. This was not an isolated event. Since 2017, India has witnessed a series of events where lives have been lost, and people’s sentiments flared due to misleading information, or, as we now call it, ‘fake news’.

The contemporary world seems to be witnessing fake news as a tool of sensational reporting, for one, that grabs the eye of the consumer better than the actual news. The nature and purpose of such fabrications has emerged as a question to be answered with a nuanced understanding of the socio-political environment we live in, as well as that of the evolution of the role of technology in human interaction.. A major concern that

then emerges is the disguise adopted by such news. Packaged under the safety net associated with authentic and objective news, such fabrications are believed by their consumers to be real, and, unless fact-checked, can lead to rampant spread of misinformation, and may even become a tool for spreading propaganda, which could prove fatal to the fabric of the society.

Fake News is any news or information that is tweaked or falsified, either as a result of misinterpretation, or to serve a particular purpose. As Hunt Allcott and Matthew Gentzkow in their paper ‘Social Media and Fake News in the 2016 Election’ explain, fake news comprises “the news articles that are intentionally and verifiably false and could mislead the readers”.

Majorly, there are two kinds of fake news - One, fake news manufactured using false data or information aimed at achieving a particular target, and second, news generated due to misinterpretation or overlap of more than one news items. The manufactured fake news is constructed such that the consumer may easily believe it to be true. Fake News could serve a number of objectives, depending on the ends the

generators of fake news may want to achieve. Its spread may directly benefit the creators of fake news, or serve to hurt the interests of another party.

Fake News in the era of Post Truth

Every epoch has its defining features; some say we may be transitioning into a post-truth era. The declaration of ‘post-truth’ as the word of the year in 2016 by the Oxford dictionary had significant implications - that the objective Truth is dead. Facts are passé. With the added vehicle of technology driving human interaction and behavior at large, the way information is exchanged is bound to pick up a few problems during its transition. In the ‘post-truth’ era, the contemporary analysis of fake news largely misses the mark for several reasons. The need to differentiate fake news from similar social satire source is important. Satire, like all literary and art forms, requires a prepared mind. In studying satire, there is a need to narrowly focus on the nature and distribution mechanisms of message propagation, and not the messages themselves. But even to state that one individual’s satire is another person’s conspiracy theory is far too simplistic. Although very difficult, the marginal cases have to be resolved by appealing to context and

detail. Thus, the need to organize or categorize ‘viral’ information comes into the context to understand its growth and trajectory, and of course, source: disclosed, anonymous, and bogus.

Media outlets should “restructure themselves to reflect the new reality of a free press, something that they have, in truth, never really been confronted with before. Hal Berghel, a fellow and professor of computer science at the University of Nevada, Las Vegas recognizes this problem not just as a supply side problem but demand side. He suggests that amelioration efforts must be directed toward unwitting victims of misinformation. Assertions in the news should be flagged before the link is clicked, not just before the story is received. Berghel proposes a meta-level crap-detecting engine in the form of an add-on or app that provides a reliability estimate for the source of any news link. By tackling this as a demand-side problem and providing users/readers with technical assistance, we can more effectively filter out and diminish the impact of lies.

This research examines the manufacturing trends of fake news by classifying them into different categories - the

different sources of fake news, the targeted audience, the manufacturing process, the targeting or triggering words, the key words and the method of creation of the news and the means of spread of the news. It focuses on the origin and escalation of fake news, particularly in the cyber-space, through which we present a case for the regulation of cyberspace by various methodologies discussed in the literature available and practiced worldwide. For this purpose, the research studies closely the news bust articles from five Indian websites working to expose fake news, namely, Alt News, Boomlive, Times Fact Check, OpIndia, Factly and Webqoof, in and related to India.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to a study by Cornell University, Fake News is, “intentionally written to mislead readers to believe false information”, and is difficult for the consumer to detect. This is because fake news involves careful construction of messages or stories and the manipulation of language to give an impression of truthfulness (Zhou & Zhang, 2008).

Across different mediums through which fake news spreads, social media has emerged as a major source, but the

most dominant one when it comes to political information (Alloct & Gentzkow, 2017). Studying the level of exposure to fake news for an average US citizen, Hunt Allcott and Matthew Gentzkow published ‘Social Media and Fake News in the 2016 Election’. Using recall method (wherein an individual is given a set of news with equal number of fake news and placebo news and is asked to recall exposure to them), they found that from the 156 articles analyzed, an individual is exposed on an average of 1.14 fake news articles.

It is important to consider how the fake news affects the real-life phenomena worldwide, including the outcome of political elections. Nick wingfield, mike Issac and Katie benner (2016) found that the world's biggest internet company’s circulation of fake news influenced the presidential elections in the States. The fake-news wildfire and revelations of its lasting effects even forced giants like Google to review their policies to curb this menace.

Source and Rise of Fake News

One of the major events of global significance to understand the intent, source and rise of fake news was the United States’ Presidential elections 2016. In this election

various social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter etc were misused to spread fake news for political motives. A study of 2760 United State (US) news websites spanning from 2014 to 2016 found that fake news content generation has been on the rise and its influence on partisan media grew in 2016 (the year of presidential election), but its overall influence on the entire media scape, in setting agenda, remained unchanged (Vargo, Guo & Amazeen 2017). It has been found by Pew research that 62% of US adults received their political news from social media in 2016. In another study, it was found out that an average American adult saw fake stories mostly in months around election time, they found consumers of fake news were more likely to believe stories that favor their preferred ideology and candidate (Golbeck et al., 2018). The consequences of such a spread has been that it has produced wrongly informed individuals that stay wrongly informed for a long time, due to echo chambers, and has resulted in emotionally antagonized people (Bakir & Mcstay, 2017).

Social Media and Fake News

With the rise of internet users globally and the sprouting up of social media platforms comes an increasing

misuse of these platforms as tools to spread fake news. In 2008 a survey conducted by the Pew Research Centre in the United States found that for people aged below 30 years, the Internet is the most important resource of news, second only to television in the case of general audiences.

Figure 2: Change in overall news sources, 2012-2017

Source: Nic Newman, "Digital News Sources," Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2017.

BROOKINGS

Fake news starts to trend.

Image: Google Trends

The picture above shows the decline of traditional news platform and the rise of social media as the primary source of news for people. This can be compared with another picture of Google trend which shows how Fake News word started rising with the rise of social media in the same period. Yet, the credibility of social media platforms as sources of news has not been dented.

Anatomy of Fake News

The life cycle of Fake News comprises of various stages and aspects which drives it towards its target. There exist various aspects in the Fake News life cycle; they include intent, origin, content, exposure, circulation and the time frame. Fake News can also be differentiated into unintentional reporting, rumors, conspiracy theories, satire, false statements and misleading reports (Alloct & Gentzkow, 2017). In another study, from a dataset consisting of 283 fake news and 203 satirical stories, the articles were classified into themes: conspiracy theories, racist themes, hyperbolic position against/ favor one person (Golbeck & others, 2018). The observations from their research were as follows - distribution of themes across articles, hyperbolic criticism of individuals appeared in

more than 2/3rd of articles, conspiracy theories in 30%, and paranormal theories in 5% of the articles. When compared to the distribution of themes in fake news/ satire stories, conspiracy theories and description of sensationalist crime were much more common in fake news than satire. This combination appeared on 19.5% of all articles, 26.9% of fake news articles, and 9.4% of satire. 213 articles had multiple themes, of which most common pair of themes was conspiracy theories and hyperbolic criticism. 55.5% Fake news articles had multiple themes as compared to 26% in satire stories (Golbeck et al., 2018).

Fake News Detection

Methodology of detection of fake news in cyberspace has been an important subject of research. Some of the methodologies for detection use a method where, by looking at the type of language used in news stories, researchers can tell the difference between true and false stories (Newman, Pennebaker, Berry, & Richards, 2003). The thoughts, emotions and motives of people can be revealed through the usage of specific words in their communication-linguistic cues, as they are rooted in the psychological experience underlying

deception (Zhou & Zhang, 2008). It has been argued by researchers that even though the Fake News spreaders might have some control over the information they have presented, but “their underlying state of mind may leak out through the style of language used to tell the story” (Newman et al., 2003, p. 672). Accordingly, these linguistic ‘slips of tongue’ can reveal underlying anxiety, guilt, or arousal (Zhou & Zhang, 2008). Pronoun use, emotionally toned words, prepositions and conjunctions are some of the features of linguistic use that have been linked to a number of behavioral and emotional outcomes associated with deception (Newman et al., 2003).

Regulatory Mechanism to Curb Fake News

As social media gains more significance as a valid news source, in particular during emergency situations and important events not covered by mainstream media, it becomes critical to regulate them and come up with tools to validate the credibility of online information. The various Fact-check media platforms have largely been autonomous (their content is not influenced by other media news) which implies that these websites are not aggressively refuting certain media and are disconnected from the nexus of news portals. Hence, they are neither influenced

by, nor influencing the Mediascape (Vargo, Guo & Amazeen 2017).

The challenges of regulation in internet space are somewhat similar to that in real space. Most of us take reasonable precautions to safeguard things of value that might exist in digital form as part of deviant subcultures, with wider social norms; there is a need for formal institutions of social control in cyberspace (Chang & Grabosk, 2017). Some of the regulatory methods suggested by researchers are through code and system design, self-regulation by the private sector and co-regulation via public and private cooperation.

Internet is the most regulable space since, through its architecture, it can reveal who someone is, where they are and what they are doing. When the machine is connected to the internet, all interactions can be monitored and identified. One of the key challenges that arise in regulation of cyberspace is that pointed out by Professor Lawrence Lessig (1999), he argued that the internet was built for research and not commerce. Its founding protocols are inherently not secure and are designed for the sharing, rather than the concealment of data. According to him (2006) cyberspace is substantially

regulated by code—computer programming and system architecture. Apart from the code and architecture methodology of regulation, the self regulation and market regulation methodology is also discussed in the literature consulted. In such a case, markets acts as regulatory institutions. The idea is that of less government intervention through various laws enacted by it. There are three forms of self-regulation commonly identified (Gunningham et al. 1998: 51): voluntary or total self-regulation (without government involvement), mandated self-regulation (involving direct government involvement) and mandated partial self-regulation (partial government involvement) (Braithwaite, 1982). The existence of pure self-regulation is quite rare because the influence of government in the form of constructing, shaping, promoting and/or facilitating self-regulation is quite pervasive (Tusikov, 2016).

In cyberspace the challenge to regulate Fake News becomes even more difficult because of cross-national activity being much more common here, hence state regulatory institutions have limitations when it comes to regulating cyberspace due to the decentralization and de-territorial character of cyberspace.

Developments in the Regulatory Space

The role which state can play via laws and regulations, in order to curb it has been very limited. It is because the functions and effectiveness of laws and regulations is limited by transnational dimensions of much cyber illegality (Grabosky et al. 2001; Katyal 2003). It is also being feared by the researchers that if code is to be regulated by government, it will lose its transparency and become architecture of control (Katyal, 2003). Another major hurdle in the way of regulation of Fake News in cyberspace is the lack of legal consistency and collaboration among states in investigating cybercrime (Chang, 2012).

From 2001 onwards, the United Nations (UN) has adopted resolutions encouraging its member states to take proper actions against cybercrime. It called on its members to note the Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention) drafted by the Council of Europe. The Budapest Convention is the first and only international convention to encourage harmonization of cyber laws and regulations, and to build cooperation among nations in controlling cyber crime. It is currently the most accepted convention on cybercrime, with 51

states ratified/ acceded as of December 2016 (Council of Europe 2001). In 2012, a new global cybercrime treaty was proposed by China, India, South Korea and a number of other regional countries at the twelfth UN Congress on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice in Salvador, Brazil. Although the proposal did not gain much support from Western countries, it might provide a good basis for a new, more inclusive convention.

RESEARCH QUESTION

This research aims to understand, examine and assess the phenomenon of Fake News prevalent in India through the following questions:

- What are the interests and discourses that promote Fake News in India today?
- What is the content of Fake News?
- What is the growth trajectory of Fake News?
- What are the existing Institutional Responses to Fake News?

METHODOLOGY

The methodology incorporated in this study is a content analysis of the fake news debunked by Alt News, WebQoof, Factly, Times Fact Check, Boomlive and OpIndia. To create a framework of classification, the news was segregated into headline, date of busting, platform of origin, tools of dissemination, source of verification and target group. Then, it was analysed based on the primary content that these websites have to offer. Within the spectrum of content analysis, the data was deciphered and understood using suitable graphs and by quantifying the time trajectory of the fake news phenomenon.

Furthermore, key informant telephonic interviews were undertaken with founders of Alt News portal and staff at Factly. The interviews were semi-structured and were intended to help us delve deeper into understanding the cumbersome phenomena of fake news.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Category of Fake News

For analyzing the trends dictating dissemination of fake news in India, we begin with categorizing the fake news

Figure 1: Categories of Fake News

debunked by these fact-checking platforms into 5 domains: Politics, Science & Education, Society & Culture, Economy & Development, and Others. With a total of 869 articles analyzed for this report, about 69% of the news pertains to the political domain. News regarding society and culture comes next, constituting 21% of fake news analyzed, followed by ‘news’ regarding science and education at 5%, and economy and development at 4.1%. Such an insight speaks volumes about the nature, intent, and target audience of fake news. The political nature of the misinformation being spread points at the

presence of political ideological factions that would be beneficiaries of public consumption of fake news.

It also underlines the potential consequences of consumption of unchecked fake news that could sway the general public consciousness against or in favour of certain political outfits, further endangering the democratic environment of the country.

Group Affiliation

The analysis of data from these websites brings out interesting patterns in terms of group affiliation, consumer base, and means of the spread of fake news in the country. Analyzing a total of 736 articles debunking fake news/information, what emerges is a striking relationship between fake news and the right wing political party, Bharatiya Janata Party. 118 of these articles seem to be affiliated to/propagated by the official members of BJP, with another 42 of articles being spread by the supporters of the party. It is a significant observation, considering the increasing use of rhetoric and propaganda made possible by spread of information that is consumed at a mass scale, to propagate a

Figure 2, Affiliation with Organization

certain ideology and its tenets. On the other hand, about 30 of these articles analyzed seem to be coming directly from the members of Indian National Congress party. Certainly, we also see also about 30 instances of fake news affiliated to leftists and liberal media platforms each. Moreover, about 50% of news articles analyzed – 357 – seem to have no direct affiliations to any party, group, or ideology. These are telling figures, since political news has for long helped the public consciousness sway in one direction, if conveyed well and conveyed often.

Social/Mainstream Media

Weight of Social Media and Mainstream Media in Spread of Fake News

Figure 3, Weight of Social Media and Mainstream Media in spread of Fake News

Social Media has clearly a much higher weightage in terms of spreading Fake News, as compared to Mainstream Media. One reason for this higher weightage could be the extensive use of social media by political parties to create a certain public discourse and narrative, a mechanism within the broader ‘perception formation’ of an ordinary voter. The correlation between the IT Cells of different political parties, the heavy reliance on social media for spreading fake news, and given the fact that an extensive portion of fake news is political in nature, can be accredited to this wider perception formation in favour of a particular ideology and discourse.

The second reason could be credited to the fact that there exists little to no regulation of the spread of fake news, by government and public institutions. The fact-checking mechanism that both Facebook and Twitter has in place is in-house in nature, and is also subject to the ‘reporting’ mechanism which allows members of the online fraternity to ‘report’ articles that may or may not uphold certain community standards. There is no ‘third-party regulation’ involved when such content appears on social media platforms. Content is only deleted or removed *after* the post appears, and by the time it has appeared, the news item may have been widely

spread, through screenshots and other storage mechanisms, long after such content has been removed.

The lower share of Mainstream media can be accredited to the presence of checks within the Media houses. A media house has editors who check and verify content before it is published. Much of the content that appears on mainstream media is often sourced from the Press Trust of India (PTI), and third-party regulators such as Press Council of India and National Broadcasting Council act as regulatory mechanisms that does not give enough leeway to Media Houses to run ‘fake news’.

Origins and Mediums of Spreading Fake News

Figure 4, Origins and Mediums of spreading Fake News

Another alarming observation that emerges from this research is the contribution of social media platforms as a tool used to spread fake news. About 460 of the total articles analyzed have been propagated via social media platforms – Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, etc – as opposed to about 90 instances of fake news spread via mainstream media, print and electronic combined. This is an extremely worrying scenario. With an increasing outreach of information technology, it is inevitable that the usage of social media platforms will soon surpass that of mainstream media platforms. Social media is easily accessible to people as a means to disseminate (mis) information and spread propaganda and rhetoric as ‘news’. When, for long, consumers of information are habitual of believing what they read or see in traditional media, it is inevitable for them to practice the same on social media, without feeling any need to verify the sources of the news or articles. It is imperative to include here, that different forms of media have been used to create and spread fake news – videos having been tampered, morphed images, memes etc.

The spread of Fake News was distinctly observed to be the highest across different Social Media platforms of Facebook, and Twitter, by individuals who are not affiliated to

any particular organisations but appear to share the views and ideologies of the same. The separate categories of Government Office Holders (positions in the Government and other public offices), and political parties, were responsible for the share of Fake News not only through their official Social Media platforms (Facebook page, Twitter Handle), but also through speeches and interviews addressed to the public.

More often than not, many of these Fake News have been picked up by Mainstream Media outlets, working in both print and digital media, thereby helping in the spread of fake news. Many reputed news outlets were found to have printed articles that were later verified by fact-checking websites to be fake in nature.

Target audience for Fake News

The target groups for the consumption of fake news across various platforms were identified for a nuanced understanding of the intent behind generating and propagating fake news. While the general public remains the target of misleading information at large, the identifiable groups seem to be divided on the base of religious and political differences.

FAKE NEWS CONSUMPTION (AS PER TARGET GROUPS)

Figure 5, Fake news consumption as per target group

Hindu community, especially, seems to be at the receiving end of fake news, followed by persons of Muslim, Christian, and other minority communities. This highlights the possible intent of the propagators of fake news to incite communal mistrust, and threaten the secular fabric of the nation at its worst, and to and to disturb the general harmony among the communities at its best. The fact that the next target group that emerged out of this research is political parties and its supporters greatly ties up with the observations mentioned

above. It is imperative to keep in mind the strong correlation between religious beliefs and politico-ideological leanings in a country like India. Further analysis should make this correlation clearer.

Time Series Analysis

Observing the trends of fake news doing the rounds, the spikes in their frequency seem to coincide with events of political or national importance. Our analysis shows a spike in instances of fake news during October - November 2018, which seems to have coincided with State Assembly elections in Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Chhattisgarh. Such news articles were mainly focused on targeting political opponents of some outfits, along with exaggerating their development achievements. Similarly, the amount of fake information floating around on social media platforms shot up tremendously during February 2019, continuing until March 2019, exactly at the time of the recent terrorist attack on CRPF in Pulwama, continuing till after the 'surgical strike' carried out by IAF troops in Balakot, Pakistan. These two events provided enough fodder for the fake news factories to come up with endless kinds of fake stories, with forms including

TIME SERIES OF FAKE NEWS: Correlating With Major Events

Figure 6, Time series analysis

images, videos of the airstrike, images etc, this phenomenon continuing till March, even when the incidents of air strikes were long over.

Yet another example is influx of fake news during October 2018 around the fake claims of violence and defaming the CPI government in Kerala post the Sabarimala temple verdict allowing women entrance to the shrine. Communal news and News on Ayodhya also occupied an important space.

Another spike was seen in the month of April with 27 Fake news stories generated. It was also the period where lot of fake news was generated on the Kathua Rape case. A sudden increase in instances of fake news was seen around the months of May, June and July, around the Hindu-Muslim divide. It was also when instances of mob lynching linked to cow slaughter and child kidnappings, mainly of persons of Muslim and Dalit communities, had shot up. Whatsapp and Facebook seem to have been the most infamous source of spreading misinformation, and rural areas the more regularly the spaces

of such incidents happening. Interestingly enough, the instances of fake news have only risen post October 2018.

Therefore, whenever an event of national concern has taken place, the makers of fake news have found immense opportunities to exploit and churn out misleading, and often divisive content.

Keyword Analysis

MOST FREQUENTLY-USED KEYWORDS

Figure 7, Top Keywords in Fake News

Content analysis of the ‘news’ debunked by the websites in consideration brings us to identify the most used keywords in these articles. Considering the constant flux of news articles that circulate on media platforms about Prime Minister Narendra Modi, it is hardly a surprise that ‘PM Narendra Modi’ is the keyword most frequently appearing in articles of fake news. The next most appearing key word, again unsurprisingly, is ‘Rahul Gandhi’, followed by the word ‘Congress’. These are followed by key words like ‘Pakistan’, ‘BJP’, ‘Balakot’, ‘Pulwama’, ‘Muslims’, ‘elections’, ‘Hindus’, & ‘Rafale’. These keywords stand testament to the political nature of fake news, and the opportunist propagation of fake news for either maligning a political faction or benefitting the propagators themselves.

Percentage Share of Top Keywords

Figure 8, Percentage Share of Top Keywords

As is clear from the graph above, 3 out of the 6 categories of keywords (Political Figures, Political Parties, and Elections - comprising 55% of the keywords) are political in nature. Political motivation - either to malign the work or ideology of the opposition or other regional parties, to push for one party's agenda by the way of creating consensus among the population beforehand, or to amplify and exaggerate one's own achievements, divert focus from one's loopholes, and create a grand narrative of homogenous political might - seems to lie at the heart of the fake-news churning factories.

Methods of Detection

Percentage Share of Methods of Detection

Figure 9, Percentage Share of Methods of Detection

Analysing the methods of detection of fake news used by the fact-checking websites, differential media reports seem to have been the highest indicators of fake news, followed by reverse image searching. An audio-visual analysis seems to work quite well in helping to detect fake news, along with personal contact with those concerned as the 4th best bet in detecting fake news. What is interesting is that cross-referencing and reverse image searching are commonplace

techniques that can be employed by ordinary individuals too, if enough awareness is created among the readers/viewers.

INSTITUTIONAL RESPONSE TO FAKE NEWS

What emerges from this analysis, thus, is an important insight into what constitutes the form and nature of fake news, with the intent to trap and engulf the public in vicious winds of fear, hatred, anger, and jingoistic fervor. Even more worrying is the ease with which the emerging platforms of social media are being used to spread such venom, with the culprits seeming anonymous and lost in the crowd of their users. What may start as an innocent jibe can quickly take on shades of hatred, fuelled by the socio-political context of the events taking place and the inability of the public to separate facts from feelings.

A significant takeaway that follows from this research is that there is limited scope of institutional mechanism for monitoring and curbing fake news. Key informant interviews revealed that, whilst Alt News - and other fact checking websites - act as first level filter, their efforts are limited to post-facto checks. If and when any culprit for propagating fake news is identified, further action may be taken legally. However, there's no strong mechanism in place to curb the

motivation for spreading fake news, or educating the general public against receiving fake news. Moreover, the vast expanses of social media platforms are extremely difficult to oversee for damaging or inciting fake news, let alone identifying news items that may not be clearly visible as fake to the first scrutiny.

There have been fatal incidents of fake news making rounds on messaging portals that have seen mob lynching take place in different parts of India: a transgender woman was killed in Hyderabad attributed to the rumors spread via services such as Whatsapp. Due to the torrential spread of this disinformation, innocent lives have been lost across the country (Arun, 2019). It is imperative that this be recognized as one of the menaces that will evolve with the evolution of technology, access to internet, and increasing comfort with using these two factors to advantages of miscreants. India has witnessed a number of mob lynchings based on fake news of cow slaughter and child kidnappings. Just one month after the Karbi Anglong lynching mentioned in the introduction to this report, three people were injured and one killed having been beaten to death in Bidar district of Karnataka, on suspicions of them being kidnappers. Incidents like these have taken place across the

country since then, killing scores of people on mere suspicions. Although though there is a lack of comprehensive strategy and policy on the part of online platforms on how to tackle the menace created by fake news, there are some steps taken by Google and other platforms to tackle this problem. Some examples are given below:

- “Fact Check” features for search results: This feature has been added to filter content which has been fact-checked on multiple levels and the corresponding information would be displayed on the search engine page. A box will clearly display the claim and who stated it, together with who checked it and, ostensibly, whether it is true. The announcement attached with this feature further elaborates how Google is not involved in the personally fact checking articles but sources it from verified sites who are driven to weed out fake and unverified claims.
- Down Ranking: To counter the spread of fake news which creates confusion, misleads or directs people towards false and offensive content, Google has recently revealed that it has updated its search algorithm with new tools. Accordingly, links and content will be down ranked based on the authenticity of the publisher, quality of publishing

material which reduces the traffic directed towards the page which hosts false or misleading information.

- Trust Project: Funded by Google, hosted by Santa Clara University, and developed in conjunction with more than 75 news organizations worldwide, the Trust Project includes a variety of factors under trust indicators such as author expertise, citations and references, and diversity of voices. News publishers would be able to provide these indicators for their online content, so that Google could store and present this information to users in Google News and other products, much like how articles in Google News now display their publication name and date.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Proactively promoting media literacy, where there is an active participation of the public in accessing, analysing and critically evaluating information, will no doubt help in limiting the influence of such hoaxes on social media platforms. On the parallel, there are certain policy recommendations which can be taken into consideration- such as, the law for making foreign technology companies to adhere to Indian rules. This will no doubt help Indian government in tackling the problem

of Fake News by tracing out the origin. However, it comes with a cost as encrypted messages will be directly handed over to the government which in turn will hamper right to privacy and be intrusive to individual's freedom of speech and expression. Even though the tech companies are taking measure to remain true to their functionalities by staying as private messaging apps, the Government has to look and make strong policies so that tech companies take necessary measure to not become broadcasting platforms. The Government needs to ensure that tech companies should be able to identify activities which indulge in broadcasting messages repeatedly. Recently, Whatsapp has been able to take steps in this direction but for it to be more efficient government has to step in. Regulating a company which operates from outside the boundary of one's country leads to many loopholes, hence Government needs to make criteria so that companies operating in India have offices which control the functioning within the boundary of the country. This makes jurisdiction of such companies easier. Additionally, a stringent punishment policy for platforms peddling fake news needs to be put in place and implemented with water-tight attitude to combat a fake news epidemic spreading in the country. Punitive measures like

suspension of licenses of such platforms by an independent body overlooking media outlets could be a way ahead, as long as these measures are not used to suppress freedom of expression. In majority of the fake news analysed, the method of detection employed was simple Google search or reverse image search which are basic techniques that with greater awareness be used by any consumer of news to verify the veracity of the news.

CONCLUSION

The study found out that the spread of fake news is mostly prevalent in the political arena and its spread upsurges to emphasize on political or communal propaganda. It was also found that the major reason for the spread of fake news was to manipulate facts to influence public opinion. Internet also plays a major role in providing an easy medium for the spread of fake news. Majorly, the fake news was targeted to the general public but was channelized according to the needs of the situation. Though it was found out that major fake news was spread in the pretext of right ideology but fake news isn't a phenomenon which just encapsulates right wing agenda religiously; other political ideology also have their fair share of

investment in this disastrous phenomenon which spreads like wildfire. There is a major correlation between catchy phrases used to make the headlines so that it easily grabs the attention of readers which again pertains to easy spread of fake news. In the mud-pool of fake news, there is an important requirement of not only individual efforts but also there is a requirement of a strong institutional mechanism to combat the spread of fake news or misinformation. In this arena of institutional response, websites like ALT News, Webqoof, Factly, Times fact Check, OpIndia and Boomlive have provided a scope to combat the issue of fake news. The study provided us with a scope to find how these institutions at various levels are finding out fake news by inspecting news on social media or on other mediums. This further indicates that social media is not only a platform for the spread of fake news but also, detection, prevention and creating awareness against fake news. The Kerala model pioneers on an institutional level to deal with fake news by inculcating lessons and classes regarding fake news detection and prevention. This paves the way for the rest of India to follow.

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APPENDIX A:

Questionnaire for key informant interviews [Prateek Sinha (ALT News) and Aila Bandagi (Factly)]

- What is your definition of fake news? (Can you show some light on the typologies?)
- Acc to your experience, what are the typologies of fake news?
- Acc to your experience, what kind of fake news is most prevalent?

- How effective and targeted is fake news?
- Which is the most effective platform acc to you for the spread of fake news?
- What is the focus area of fake news industry?
- Acc to you, which group is most susceptible to tale up fake news at face value?
- Can you trace a linkage between hate speech and fake news given in the common lens of elections?
- In your experience, is there a way to tackle the menace of fake news?
- Can you elaborate on what happens after the person manufacturing fake news is found out

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